

First Records of Trypetini (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetinae) from Europe

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Recently, Korneyev & Korneyev (2015) reviewed new records of mining Trypetinae found in Ukraine. In addition, a few specimens of that tribe are recorded from other countries, mostly based on photographs published on the site Diptera.Info or specimens deposited in Royal Belgian Institute of Natural History, Brussels (BINH) and Diptera Collection of the Faculty of Biology and Geology, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania (DCBBU).

Hemilea dimidiata (Costa, 1844)

Material. **Spain:** Galicia, Meis, 12.05.2015 ([based on a photograph](#)); **Slovenia:** Ljubno, 23.05, 9.06.2009, 1♂, 1♀ (M. Cvenkel) (based on photographs of a [male](#) and a [female](#)).

Distribution. Austria, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Slovenia, Switzerland; Russia (Moscow Region, Caucasus); Turkey; Ukraine (Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015); Slovenia (Cvenkel, 2015, as "*H. pulchella*"); **Spain** (first record).

Stemonocera cornuta (Scopoli, 1763)

Material. **Bulgaria:** Rila Mountains, between Beli Iskar and Borovets (Borowetz), 42.258867°N 23.568042°E, 1437 m, spruce forest (Picea abies dominant forest), near a small brook. 13.07.2012, 1♂ (Kolcsar) (DCBBU). **Romania:** Southern Carpathians, High Sebes, Daşa, Şuga [c. 45.766667° N 23.633333° E], 9.07.1938, 1♂ (R. Leruth) (BINH).

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Poland; Switzerland, United Kingdom; Romania; Russia (Leningrad, Moscow Regions, Western and Eastern Siberia; Far East); Eastern Kazakhstan; Kyrgyzstan; North-Eastern China, Japan (see Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015); **Bulgaria** (first record).

Stemonocera spinifrons (Schroeder, 1913)

Material. **Ukraine:** Transcarpathian Region: Turkul Mountain, 48.110046°N 24.490867°E, 1180 m, 17.07.2014, 1♂ (Kolcsar) (DCBBU).

Distribution. Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Poland; Switzerland, Ukraine; United Kingdom; Romania; Russia (Leningrad, Moscow Regions, Western and Eastern Siberia; Far East); Eastern Kazakhstan; Kyrgyzstan; North-Eastern China, Japan (see Korneyev & Korneyev, 2015). This is another new locality of this spot, recently recorded from Ukraine.

References

Korneyev, V. A. & Korneyev, S. V. (2015) First records of the trypetine mining flies (Diptera: Tephritidae: Trypetini) from Ukraine. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 6(3), 45–47.

Figs. 1–5. *Stemonocera cornuta* (1–3) and *S. spinifrons* (4–5): 1 — wing; 2 — head left (specimen from BINH); 3, 4 — habitus, left (specimens from DCBBU); 5 — biotope of *S. spinifrons*.

Cvenkel, M. (2015) *Hemilea pulchella*. http://www.agrozoos.net/jsp/Gallery_one_image.jsp?id_gallery=5cbb19f281ab4e3d83a2e893341fc311. Accessed 20.12.2015.

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